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SHEMAIEVA H. V.

Department of Documentation and Ukrainian Language, National Aerospace University

M. E. Zhukovsky «KhAI» (Kharkiv, Ukraine), e-mail: annashemaeva@ukr.net,

ORCID 0000-0002-1053-989X

KOSTYRKO T. M.

Scientific Library, Admiral Makarov National University of Shipbuilding (Mykolaiv, Ukraine),

e-mail: tamara.kostyrko@nuos.edu.ua, ORCID 0000-0002-4175-9975

GRABAR, N. H.

State Biotechnology University (Kharkiv, Ukraine), e-mail: grabar-ng@ukr.net,

ORCID 0000-0002-5120-0382

International Cooperation in the Sphere of LIS: Analysing the Materials of the BOBCATSSS Conference

Objective. The article highlights the results of analysing the materials of the International Scientific Conference BOBCATSSS (2012–2023) within the framework of which current topics of library and information science, education, and practice are discussed. **Methods.** The study of international professional cooperation is based on the use of a complex of scientific methods, in particular: analysis and synthesis, static analysis, bibliometric analysis, and scientometric diagnostics. **Results.** The expansion of the geographical boundaries in international cooperation has been determined. The thematic aspects that were discussed during 2012–2023 are revealed. Attention is focused on international co-authorship as a priority direction of professional interaction. The peculiarities of project professional interaction in terms of quantitative, substantive, and organizational aspects have been revealed. It was established that the majority of international projects announced at the Conference are implemented on the basis of cooperation between universities of European countries. **Conclusions.** International cooperation of European countries develops, first of all, at the organizational level and is characterized by the joint participation of several universities from different countries for the preparation of the Conference. Secondly, we can observe the development of international research, which is manifested at the level of international co-authorship and international projects. Analysing the materials of the BOBCATSSS Conference attests to the innovative activity of European universities that train personnel for the information and library sphere and raises the issue of intensifying international cooperation of Ukrainian professionals and scientists.

Keywords: library and information sciences (LIS); international cooperation; scientific communications; co-authorship; international project activity; bibliometric analysis; BOBCATSSS Conference

Introduction

In the modern conditions of crisis phenomena, there is a significant rethinking of traditional approaches to scientific and educational activities in general and in the library and information sphere in particular. The development of the library and information sphere requires monitoring and tracking of global trends in this field, determining the directions and opportunities for more active involvement in international cooperation.

At the European level, the European Association for Library and Information Science BOBCATSSS (<https://bobcatsss.info/>), former EUCLID (European Association for Library and Information Education and Research), is of great importance. Its mission is: to promote the exchange of students and staff among members of the association, mutual recognition of educational programs or their parts, development of cooperation in the implementation of research programs and projects, mutual exchange of information about scientific research, and development of educational programs, support of weaker universities by more powerful ones, publication of a newsletter, cooperation with the programs of the European Union.

Under the auspices of the BOBCATSSS Association, students, teachers, researchers, and information specialists from the University of a certain country have been organizing the BOBCATSSS Conference annually since 1993. Its purpose is to strengthen international cooperation in various areas of information and library science and education. Therefore, researching the materials of this Conference becomes especially relevant.

To study the processes of professional scientific communication and international cooperation, scientists usually choose individual titles of journals. Indian researcher Das P. K. (2015) highlights research collaborations during 2007–2013 based on publications in the “Journal of Informetrics”. Another researcher, Thavamani Kotti (2015), chose for analysis the international electronic journal Collaborative Librarianship, which covers a wide range of issues related to library collaboration at different levels of cooperation: local, regional, national, and international. According to the research results, the scientist established an increase in international interaction (Thavamani, 2015). Prieto-Gutierrez J. J. and Segado-Boj F. (2019) presented the bibliometric analysis of publications in the leading Indian journal “Annals of Library and Information Studies” for the period 2011–2017. They compared the identified research trends in LIS with other professional publications in India, Asia, and the world.

A significant number of researchers study the level of cooperation in the library and information sphere on the basis of specialized publications indexed in the Web of Science and Scopus scientometric databases. Researchers distinguish types and directions of authorship, author productivity, degree and index of cooperation, geography of cooperation and partnership, and features of joint preparation of publications. A history of co-citation analysis for the intellectual structure of informatics in the period 2011–2020 and changes in this structure is provided by Zhao D. with Strotmann A. (2022). Many researchers analyze the thematic content of scientific publications, study networks, and channels of scientific communication between universities. Among them, it is worth noting the scientists who applied cluster analysis and determined the role of the countries of the world in LIS research during 1963–2012 (Hosseini & Erfanmanesh, 2015).

Much less attention is paid to the research of conference materials. The formats of conferences and the analysis of conference materials in the field of LIS in conditions of limited physical communication are the subject of Ukrainian scientists’ attention (Kolesnykova, 2020). Researchers who are active participants in this forum are addressing the disclosure of various aspects of scientific communications within the framework of BOBCATSSS International Conference. Among them, it is worth noting the bibliometric analysis of conference materials for 1998–2001 (Klobcar & Juznic, 2002). Recent research includes Sveum Tor (2013) and Golub A., Cupar D., and Pjanić V. (2021). The first author's attention focuses on the problems of interaction, in particular between teachers and students, during the joint preparation of publications (Sveum, 2013). The second research is devoted to the quantitative and qualitative determination concerning the topics of publications in the materials of the BOBCATSSS Conference for the period 2015–2020 (Golub, Cupar, & Pjanić, 2021). Research materials were presented at the Conference in 2021, where all documents related to digital content, digitalization, and information and communication technologies were reviewed in detail.

The authors of this work (H. Shemaieva and T. Kostyrko) took part in the BOBCATSSS Conference in 2022 and presented the first stage of research on international scientific cooperation on the basis of co-authorship (2012–2021) (Shemaieva & Kostyrko, 2022). The second stage of research into the conference materials is aimed at further identifying priority aspects of international cooperation.

The purpose of the publication is to highlight the results of analysing the scientific materials of the BOBCATSSS Conferences during 2012–2023 in the aspect of international cooperation in the field of LIS.

Results and Discussion

During the research, the strategy to familiarise the texts of the conference materials was used by applying the methods of analysis and synthesis, bibliometrics, and scientometric diagnostics. Only reports of articles were used for analysis. Posters, seminars, PechaKucha, etc. were not subject to analysis. In addition to defining statistical data by countries, authors, and organizations and identifying the number of joint publications, attention is focused on thematic aspects and international project cooperation.

It was found that the BOBCATSSS Conference was held in 16 countries from its beginning in 1993 to 2023. Most often, the Conference was organized by Hungarian universities (1993–1998, 2005, 2011, 2022). In several countries, the Conference was organized twice. These are Poland (2000, 2003), Latvia (2004, 2018), Czech Republic (2007, 2015), Croatia (2008, 2019), Portugal (2009, 2021), France (2017, 2020) (Table 1).

Table 1

Organization of the Conference by Years, Countries, and Topics

Year	Venue Country	Country	Topic
1	2	3	4
1993	Budapest	Hungary	The Role of Libraries Today, Tomorrow and Beyond
1994	Budapest	Hungary	The Future of Librarianship
1995	Budapest	Hungary	Marketing and Development of New Information Products and Services in Europe
1996	Budapest	Hungary	Quality of Information Services
1997	Budapest	Hungary	New Book Economy
1998	Budapest	Hungary	Shaping the Knowledge Society
1999	Bratislava	Slovakia	Learning Society – Learning Organization – Lifelong Learning (LLL)
2000	Krakow	Poland	Intellectual property vs. the right to knowledge
2001	Vilnius	Lithuania	Knowledge, Information and Democracy in the Open Society: the Role of Library and Information Sector
2002	Portorož	Slovenia	Human@Beings and Information Specialists. Future Skills, Qualifications, Positioning
2003	Torun	Poland	Information Policy and the European Union
2004	Riga	Latvia	Library and Information in Multicultural Societies
2005	Budapest	Hungary	Librarianship in the information age
2006	Tallinn	Estonia	Information, Innovation, Responsibility: Information professional in the Network Society
2007	Prague	Czech Republic	Marketing information services
2008	Zadar	Croatia	Providing access to information for everyone
2009	Porto	Portugal	Challenges for the new information professional

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2010	Parma	Italy	Bridging the digital divide
2011	Szombathely	Hungary	Finding new ways
2012	Amsterdam	Netherlands	Information in e-Motion
2013	Ankara	Turkey	From Collections to Connections: Turning Libraries “Inside-Out”
2014	Barcelona	Spain	Library (r)evolution: Promoting sustainable information practices
2015	Brno	Czech Republic	Design, Innovation, Participation
2016	Lyon	France	Information. Libraries. Democracy
2017	Tampere	Finland	Quality of Life through information
2018	Riga	Latvia	The Power of Reading
2019	Osijek	Croatia	Information and Technology transforming lives: Connection, Interaction, Innovation
2020	Paris	France	Information management fake news and disinformation
2021	Porto	Portugal	Digital Transformation
2022	Debrecen	Hungary	Data and Information Science
2023	Oslo	Norway	A New Era - Exploring the Possibilities and Expanding the Boundaries

The number of countries represented at the Conference ranges from 16 to 29 (2012 – 27 countries, 2013 – 28 countries, 2014 – 25 countries, 2015 – 23 countries, 2016 – 25 countries, 2017 – 29 countries, 2018 – 17 countries, 2019 – 22 countries, 2020 – 19 countries, 2021 – 16 countries, 2022 – 16, 2023 – 24 ones). In total, representatives of 43 countries participated in the Conference during the studied period. In recent years (2022-2023), experts from countries that did not participate in the Conference before: Bangladesh, Brazil, Iceland, Kenya, Romania, and Ukraine joined the Conference. This testifies to the expansion of the geographical boundaries of BOBCATSSS participants and the development of international scientific communications.

As a rule, students and teachers from two or three universities from different countries take part in the preparation of the Conference, which indicates the expansion of international professional communications between European universities and the involvement of library specialists in this process in 2022 (Table 2).

Table 2

Organizational Interaction in the Preparation of Conferences

Year	City	Country	University
2018	Riga	Latvia	1)University of Latvia 2)Eötvös Loránd University, Hungary
2019	Osijek	Croatia	1)Department of Information Sciences, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences at University of Osijek, Croatia 2)The Hague University of Applied Sciences, Netherlands 3)Uppsala University and Linnaeus University, Sweden

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2020	Paris	France	1)Institut Francilien d'Ingénierie des Services (IFIS), Gustave Eiffel University, Paris, France 2)University of Library Studies and Information Technologies (ULSIT), Sofia, Bulgaria
2021	Porto	Portugal	1)Porto Accounting and Business School - Porto Polytechnic (ISCAP), Portugal 2)University of Library Studies and Information Technologies (ULSIT), Sofia, Bulgaria 3) University of Leon, Spain
2022	Debrecen	Hungary	1)Faculty of Informatics and Faculty of Humanities of University of Debrecen, Hungary 2)University and National Library, Hungary 3)Media, Information and Design of the University of Applied Sciences and Arts Hannover, Germany
2023	Oslo	Norway	1)Department of Archivistics, Library and Information Science of Oslo Metropolitan University, Norway 2)Department of Information studies at University College London, UK 3)Swedish School of Library and Information Science of University of Boras, Sweden

This approach to organizing the Conference allows us to establish and strengthen relationships between universities. Therefore, within the framework of our research, we additionally monitored how international communications correlate with each other in the process of joint organization of the Conference, joint preparation of a report, and joint project activities.

Reading conference publications made it possible to determine the topics that were subject to discussion during 2012–2016. Despite a certain thematic orientation of each year, among the relevant topics are information resources and sources of information, information channels, social networks and media, electronic libraries and their role in society, LIS education (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Current Topics of the BOBCATSSS Conference Materials During 2012–2016

In 2017, the main thematic blocks were: Library, Information, Interactive media. The largest number of reports related to library innovations and trends in library and information education. The theme of 2018 was focused on reading: reading skills in the digital space, experience of libraries in promoting reading, reading culture, and communication. The issues about the preservation of cultural heritage and academic integrity were also raised. The research by Hungarian librarians (National Széchényi Library) by Andor Nagy and Máté Tóth, aimed at comparing the priorities of digitalization of cultural values in the libraries of European countries, attracts attention among the materials of 2018. The researchers found different motivations for digitization in libraries in the south, north, east, and west of Europe, as well as among national-level, academic, and public libraries. In particular, they established that for Eastern countries, the focus on conservation and ensuring creative use is of great importance, while in other countries, commercial goals and satisfaction of leisure needs prevail (Nagy & Toth, 2018).

In order to attract participants from different countries, support scientific communication, and further development of international interaction, the best reports are determined within BOBCATSSS Conferences. So, the research of Lisa Morrison, Graduate Student, and Terry Weech, Associate Professor of School of Information Sciences, University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign, USA, was recognized as the best report of 2018. Alina Stoicescu (University of Copenhagen, Denmark) and Isto Huvila (Uppsala University, Sweden) received awards for the best works of BOBCATSSS 2019.

During 2019–2023, the topics of reports were diversified in accordance with the needs of information and library structures, and modern challenges. This period includes the following current topics (the participants of the Conference addressed to them every year): formation of information and media literacy; management of digital data and collections; Copyright; open access, open resources (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Current Topics Discussed During 2019–2023

Compared to the 2012–2016 period, the emphasis on research, personnel training, and professional activity in 2019–2023, in our opinion, is due to the development of open science.

Among the main topics of the reports in 2019, we can also highlight the social roles of information institutions, innovative technologies, and the information profession, which is becoming more and more interdisciplinary. The interesting report is on the transformation of the LIS department into a transdisciplinary iSchool model at Linnaeus University (Sweden), which united disparate departments, disciplines and non-academic institutions to train personnel that meet today's demands (Golub, 2019).

Most of the reports in 2020 were devoted to the declared theme of the Conference: countering fake news, fake information, predatory journals through the development of critical thinking, academic integrity, and the formation of information and media literacy.

The BOBCATSSS-2021 Conference was virtual due to the global COVID-19 crisis. Digitization of cultural heritage documents, preservation, transmission and exchange of information and knowledge in the network space, distance learning, management of information, data and digital services, online reading, copyright law, and other issues were discussed during the Conference.

In 2022, the main attention was paid to information and data, the use of open educational resources, the problems of supporting science and scientific communications by library specialists, developing Data Science competencies among students, and other relevant issues. Undoubtedly, the key reports dedicated to open science, cognitive information communications, and artificial intelligence are interesting and extraordinary.

New opportunities for the library and information profession became the subject of discussion at BOBCATSSS-2023 (Zenodo, 2023). Among them, we can highlight the convergent development of libraries, museums, and archives; problems of international scientific cooperation in the direction of digital curation; evaluation of digital content; new approaches to the organization of LIS education; new roles and prospects for the development of libraries, etc.

Undoubtedly, the exchange of information within the Conference of students, teachers, information specialists, library workers, and representatives of other structures promptly reflects the processes and trends of the branch development and contributes to the deepening of international professional cooperation. Joint preparation and implementation of international projects and cooperation of researchers based on co-authorship are key factors in this aspect.

Modern forms and channels of scientific communication contribute to the unification of researchers from different countries to organize and conduct joint research, and preparation of joint publications. In general, local, national, and international co-authorship can be distinguished in scientific communications. Local co-authorship is understood as joint research by authors who work in the same institution and prepared a scientific publication through joint efforts. National co-authorship is the result of cooperation between researchers from different institutions and organizations in the same country. International co-authorship is a scientific collaboration of researchers from different countries, the result of which is a joint publication (Shemaieva & Kostyrko, 2022).

In general, within the framework of the research, the total number of co-authored documents during 2019–2022 and the number of international co-authored documents were determined (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. The Number of Co-authored Documents in Relation to the Total Number of Documents by Years

As can be seen from the diagram, co-authoring is a common practice among academics and educators participating in BOBCATSSS Conferences. Along with this, international co-authorship is less common but it is growing. The analysis process revealed high activity of international cooperation between teachers, students, information specialists, library workers, management specialists, and other researchers from Hachette University, Turkey; University of Zagreb, Croatia; University of Library Studies and Information Technologies, Bulgaria; Faculty of Informatics, University of Debrecen; Hungary; National Szechenyi Library, Hungary; Inland Norway University of Applied Sciences, Hamar, Norway; Oslo Metropolitan University, Oslo, Norway.

In total, the authors identified 29 publications of international co-authorship during 2012–2023 (Table 3).

Table 3

The Number of General Publications Prepared by Authors from Different Countries

Year	The number of documents	The number of authors	International interaction between countries in the joint preparation of materials
2012	4	15	1)AU+DE, 2)NO+BD, 3)DK+RO, 4)BG+TR+HR
2013	2	8	1)TR+BW+LV, 2)BG+HR+TR+FR
2014	4	10	1)JP+US, 2)IT+CA, 3)ES+US, 4)TR+HR
2015	1	2	1)CA+US
2016	2	4	1)US+ZA, 2)US+HU
2017	2	4	1)HR+SE, 2)UK+NO
2018	-	-	-
2019	3	9	1)NO+HU, 2)US+HR, 3)JP+NO
2020	1	3	1)BG+US
2021	-	-	-
2022	4	11	1)IP+US, 2)HU+US, 3)HU+RO, 4)HU+PL
2023	6	25	1)DK+SE+NO+IS, 2)PT+BR, 3)BG+IT+FI, 4)HU+US, 5)US+CA+BD, 6)FI+NO

The conducted research about co-authorship within the Conference made it possible to establish that student co-authorship is developing in the scientific and educational environment of the library and information sphere. The researchers of the conference materials drew attention to this: Jelke Nijboer (2012), who underlined the co-authorship of students with teachers as an important educational strategy, and T. Sveum (2013), who, as a result of the BOBCATSSS-2012 study, found 17 joint publications of students and teachers and 6 papers of student co-authorship (between students) (Shemaieva & Kostyrko, 2022; Sveum, 2013). The development of co-authorship with students and the implementation of communications by students at an International Conference is indeed important not only for educational strategies but also for the inclusion of students in scientific communications at the international level.

It was possible to track student co-authorship during the study of the materials for 2019 and 2023 (Table 4). This is due to the fact that many Proceedings and Abstracts of BOBCATSSS Conferences do not have specific information about its participants.

Based on the materials of the 2019 and 2023 Conferences, it can be concluded that students from almost all countries participating in them are actively involved in scientific research and

dissemination of their results at BOBCATSSS International Conferences, both in individual publications and in co-authorship with teachers/professors. The most active are students from Croatia, Norway, and Germany.

Table 4

Student Publications (Individual and Co-authored)

Year	bachelor			master			postgraduate		
	individual	co-authored	International	individual	co-authored	International	individual	co-authored	International
2019	3	2	1	6	9	-	5	5	-
2023	3	9	-	1	2	-	1	3	-

As we can see from Table 4, in 2019 there was student participation in the preparation of one document of international co-authorship. These two undergraduate students together with their scientific supervisor professor and assistant to the professor (University of Osijek, Croatia) and a professor from the USA (The Simmons School of Library and Information Science) argued the importance of an online forum for the treatment of Alzheimer's disease.

An undergraduate student's report, co-authored with a master's student from Hungary (Eötvös Loránd University), which compares data science-related programs and disciplines in higher education institutions in Hungary and the Philippines, is also noteworthy. The research of a student and her teacher from Portugal (University of Coimbra, Faculty of Arts and Humanities) is also interesting, where they justify preprints as a new model of publishing in a repository and as an operational method of modern scientific communication. Collaboration between web archivists and digital humanitarians in the fields of data mining, data visualization, and artificial intelligence is having an impact. Note that Ukrainian researchers emphasize the development of multifaceted communication links in the library and information environment. In particular, one of these forms defines the interaction of teachers, scientists, and practicing librarians with students (Grabar & Kislyuk, 2023).

Also, in the process of studying the conference materials, the most active authors were identified. Koizumi Masaroni, who is one of the famous Japanese experts in the field of library management (University of Tsukuba, Japan), has the largest number of publications. He submitted both individual research materials and co-authorship during 2019–2023. Tania Todorova has fewer publications: Chair of BOBCATSSS Association 2021–2023, Chair "Interfaculty Chair 'ICT in Library Studies, Education and Cultural Heritage'", University of Library Studies and Information Technologies, Bulgaria. She actively develops international partnerships with universities in different countries. It is worth noting that it was she who contributed to the establishment of professional contacts among teachers of specialized departments of the Kharkiv State Academy of Culture and the National Aerospace University named after M. E. Zhukovsky "KHAI", Kharkiv, Ukraine at the level of the Cooperation Agreement with the University of Library Studies and Information Technologies, Bulgaria and joining the international project Digital Education for Crisis Situations: Times when there is no alternative (DECriS) as participants in filling out questionnaires and online participation of teachers of Kharkiv, Kharkiv, Ukraine, and library specialists at the scientific library of the National University of Shipbuilding, Mykolaiv, Ukraine in Multiplier Events within the scope of the project DECriS.

In general, in the process of analysing the materials of the BOBCATSSS Conference, a high level of international cooperation was determined in the direction of the implementation of joint international projects between European universities and European universities of other

countries, in particular with the USA, Canada, and Japan. During the research period, specialists from Germany and Croatia took part in 10 projects, Hungary – in 7 projects, Turkey, Bulgaria, and France – in 6 projects (Table 5). It is worth noting that reports on the joint preparation and implementation of international projects are submitted both jointly and individually. As can be seen from Table 5, the largest number of projects (9) was presented in 2012 and 2023, and the smallest (1) in 2018.

Table 5

Communications within the Conference about International Projects

Year	The number of projects	International projects by countries
2012	9	1) Hungary+Croatia, 2) USA+Germany, 3) Australia+Germany, 4) Norway+Bangladesh, 5) Sweden+Denmark, 6) Turkey+Croatia, 7) Great Britain+Croatia, 8) Germany+Netherlands, 9) Bulgaria+Croatia+Turkey
2013	3	1) Turkey+Denmark, 2) Poland+Mexico, 3) Bulgaria+Croatia+Turkey+France
2014	2	1) France+USA, 2) Netherlands+Germany+China
2015	3	1)Czech Republic+Finland, 2)Croatia+Turkey, 3)USA+Canada
2016	4	1) Czech Republic+France, 2) USA+South Africa+France, 3)Hungary+USA, 4)Poland+Lithuania+Latvia+Norway
2017	5	1) Italy+Canada, 2) France+USA, 3) France+China+Netherlands, 4) France+South Korea+Netherlands, 5)Germany+Netherlands+China
2018	1	1) USA+Great Britain+Germany
2019	5	1) Croatia+Turkey+Spain+Sweden+Austria+Germany+Poland+Italy, 2) Denmark+Germany+Hungary+Norway+Sweden+Switzerland, 3) Croatia+Slovakia+Slovenia+Czech Republic+Poland, 4) USA+Croatia, 5)Norway+Sweden+Finland
2020	1	1) USA+Bulgaria, 2) Bulgaria+Netherlands+Italy
2021	1	1) Great Britain+Ireland+Finland+Netherlands+Germany+Austria
2022	4	1) Japan+USA, 2) Hungary+USA, 3) Hungary+Poland, 4) Spain+Portugal
2023	7	1) Brazil+Portugal, 2) Croatia+Germany+Spain+Bulgaria, 3)Bulgaria+Italy+Finland, 4)Hungary+USA, 5)USA+Canada+Bangladesh, 6)Finland+Norway 7)Italy+UK+Netherlands +Hungary+Germany

Familiarization with the conference materials, which outline the features, directions, and results of joint project activities at the international level, allows us to confirm our previous conclusions that the modernization of information and library education in European countries is primarily aimed at the development of international partnership and social dialogue (Shemaieva & Grabar, 2021). The implementation of international projects is aimed at: the development of communication skills of library workers; digitization of cultural heritage; collaboration between business, library and information sphere and science; joint creation and use of open educational resources; development of international research, training of information and library personnel; changing the role of libraries in supporting scientific communications; interaction with communities. The duration of contacts between the cooperation parties, the competence of the participants, and personal characteristics are important for international cooperation. Today, international exchange programs and projects between universities and colleges are an integral part of the educational programs of many institutions.

Conclusions

The conducted analysis of International Conferences contributes to a clearer understanding of the changes taking place in the information and library sphere and forecasting of further development strategies.

International cooperation of European countries develops, first of all, at the organizational level and is characterized by the joint participation of several universities from different countries for the preparation of the conference. Secondly, the development of international research is taking place, which is manifested in the preparation of joint publications (international co-authorship) and international projects aimed at developing the communication skills of library workers; digitization of cultural heritage; collaboration between business, library, and information sphere and science; joint creation and use of open educational resources; strengthening of digital infrastructure; formation of new professional skills.

The thematic content of the conferences shows not only the development of relevant research, and educational and practical directions in foreign experience but also allows to determine the directions of inclusion of Ukrainian professionals in international movements and projects. Of course, English language proficiency, geographical distance, and cultural proximity are important factors that have a positive effect on scientific international cooperation.

An important condition for the development of professional international interaction in the modern socio-communicative environment of the library sphere is the deployment of the organization of international communicative events; participation in international scientific research; training of personnel who have the latest tools of professional activity; initiation of international projects; international co-authorship. Activation of international co-authorship will contribute to the understanding of cultural, linguistic, political, technological, and professional features.

In general, the analysis of the materials of the BOBCATSSS Conference confirms the innovative activity of European universities, which train personnel for the information and library field, and raises the issue of intensifying international cooperation of Ukrainian professionals and scientists.

REFERENCES

- Das, P. K. (2015). Authorship pattern and research collaboration of Journal of Informetrics. *International Journal of Information Dissemination and Technology*, 5(1), 53-62. Retrieved from <http://surl.li/oqlkt> (in English)
- Golub, A., Cupar, D., & Pjanić, V. (2021, January). Is BOBCATSSS preparing its participants for digital transformation? Topic analysis of papers presented at BOBCATSSS Conferences from 2015 to 2020. In *Digital Transformation: Book of Abstracts at BOBCATSSS 2021 Virtual Conference*, (pp. 201-207). Porto, Portugal. doi: <https://doi.org/10.34630/bobcatsss.vi.4977> (in English)
- Golub, K. (2019, January). From a library and information science department to a transdisciplinary, university-wide iSchool: a model of Linnaeus University. In *Information and Technology Transforming Lives: Connection, Interaction, Innovation. Proceedings of the XXVII Bobcatsss Symposium* (pp.15-22). Osijek, Croatia. Retrieved from https://bib.irb.hr/datoteka/1033483.bobcatsss_proceedings4.pdf (in English)
- Grabar, N., & Kislyuk, L. (2023). Professional communication in the scientific and educational communicative environment of the library sphere. *Bulletin of the Book Chamber*, 6, 36-41. doi: [https://doi.org/10.36273/2076-9555.2023.6\(323\).36-41](https://doi.org/10.36273/2076-9555.2023.6(323).36-41) (in English)

- Hosseini, E., & Erfanmanesh, M. (2015). Cross-time analysis of countries co-authorship networks in LIS research. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, 1, 1-11. Retrieved from <http://surl.li/oqllv> (in English)
- Klobcar, M., & Juznic, P. (2002). Bibliometrical and bibliographical analyses of BOBCATSSS proceedings (1998-2001). In *Proceedings of the 10th International Bobcatsss Symposium on Library and Information Science* (pp.16-25). Portoroz, Slovenia. (in English)
- Kolesnykova, T. O. (2020). Conference time in the library and information sciences. Part 1: Conference proceedings and proceedings (conference) paper. *University Library at a New Stage of Social Communications Development. Conference Proceedings*, 5, 95-106. doi: https://doi.org/10.15802/unilib/2020_220640 (in English)
- Nagy, A., & Toth, M. (2018, January). Comparative analysis of digitalization priorities set by libraries in Europe. In *Proceedings of the XXVI Bobcatsss Symposium* (pp. 18-23), University of Latvia. Riga, Latvia. Retrieved from <http://surl.li/mfykb> (in English)
- Prieto-Gutierrez, J. J., & Segado-Boj, F. (2019). Annals of library and information studies: A bibliometric analysis of the journal and comparison with the top library and information studies journals in Asia and worldwide (2011-2017). *The Serials Librarian*, 77(1/2), 38-48, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/0361526X.2019.1637387> (in English)
- Shemaieva, H., & Grabar, N. (2021). Proiektno-oriientovane profesiine spilkuvannia yak umova rozvytku bibliotechnoho komunikatyvnoho seredovyshcha [Project-oriented professional communication as a condition for the development of a library communicative environment]. *Library Science. Record Studies. Informology*, 1, 5-11. doi: <https://doi.org/10.32461/2409-9805.1.2021.229835> (in Ukrainian)
- Shemaieva, H., & Kostyrko, T. (2022). *Co-authorship at the BOBCATSSS Conference (2012-2021): an aspect of international professional interaction*. Zenodo. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6534738> (in English)
- Sveum, T. (2013). Collaborative writing at Bobcatsss. Two heads are better than one? *New Library World*, 114(5/6), 214-227. doi: 10.1108/03074801311326849 (in English)
- Thavamani, K. (2015). A study of authorship patterns and collaborative research in collaborative librarianship, 2009-2014. *Collaborative Librarianship*. 7(2), 84-95. Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.du.edu/collaborativelibrarianship/vol7/iss2/6> (in English)
- Zenodo. (2023, January). *Proceedings of the BOBCATSSS 2023 Conference: A New era – exploring the possibilities and expanding the boundaries*, Oslo Metropolitan University (OsloMet). Oslo, Norway. Retrieved from <https://zenodo.org/records/8136825> (in English)
- Zhao, D. & Strotmann, A. (2022). Intellectual structure of information science 2011–2020: an author co-citation analysis. *Journal of Documentation*, 78(3), 728-744. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-06-2021-0119> (in English)

SHEMAIEVA H. V.

Кафедра документознавства та української мови, Національний аерокосмічний університет ім. М. С. Жуковського «ХАІ» (Харків, Україна),
e-mail: annashemaeva@ukr.net, ORCID 0000-0002-1053-989X

KOSTYRKO T. M.

Наукова бібліотека, Національний університет кораблебудування ім. адмірала Макарова, (Миколаїв, Україна), e-mail: tamara.kostyrko@nuos.edu.ua, ORCID 0000-0002-4175-9975

GRABAR N. H.

Державний біотехнологічний університет (Харків, Україна), e-mail: grabar-ng@ukr.net, ORCID 0000-0002-5120-0382

Міжнародне співробітництво у сфері LIS: аналіз матеріалів конференції BOVCATSSS

Мета. Висвітлюються результати аналізу матеріалів міжнародної наукової конференції BOVCATSSS (2012–2023), в межах якої дискутуються актуальні теми бібліотечно-інформаційної науки, освіти і практики. **Методика.** Вивчення міжнародного професійного співробітництва ґрунтується на використанні комплексу наукових методів, зокрема: аналізу і синтезу, статичного аналізу, бібліометричного аналізу та наукометричної діагностики. **Результати.** Визначено розширення географічних меж міжнародного співробітництва. Розкрито тематичні аспекти, які обговорювалися протягом 2012–2023 рр. Акцентовано увагу на міжнародному співавторстві як пріоритетному напрямі професійної взаємодії. Виявлено особливості проектної професійної взаємодії за кількісними, змістовними та організаційними аспектами. Встановлено, що більшість міжнародних проектів, про які повідомляється на конференції, реалізується на засадах співпраці університетів європейських країн. **Висновки.** Міжнародне співробітництво європейських країн розвивається, по-перше, на організаційному рівні та характеризується спільною участю декількох університетів із різних країн для підготовки конференції. По-друге, відбувається розвиток інтернаціональних досліджень, що проявляється на рівні міжнародного співавторства та міжнародних проектів. Аналіз матеріалів конференції BOVCATSSS засвідчує інноваційну активність європейських університетів, що здійснюють підготовку кадрів для інформаційно-бібліотечної сфери та порушує питання активізації міжнародної співпраці українських професіоналів та науковців.

Ключові слова: бібліотечно-інформаційні науки (LIS); міжнародне співробітництво; наукові комунікації; співавторство; міжнародна проектна діяльність; бібліометричний аналіз; конференція BOVCATSSS

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